

An overview of the roles of TVET and ACET Sectors in improving employment prospects for South African youth

Selina Ramapela^{#1}

*University of Limpopo, Sovenga, South Africa
Department of Education Studies, Faculty of Humanities*

Reginald Botshabeng Monyai^{#2}

*University of South Africa
Department of Adult Community and Continuing Education*

ABSTRACT

The South African youth face challenges of unemployment as a result of their lack of skills and relevant education. The majority come from poor social backgrounds with very minimal or without any form of income. The country's education policies are conceded to address the injustices caused by the past regime. This article reflects and acknowledge the widening gap of poverty irrespective of available opportunities for the young generations to uplift their lives. The article provide qualitative evidence that validates the positive contribution of the TVET and ACET sectors to tap the poverty margins. The qualitative approach with case study design was employed to provide the overview of the research enquiry. The qualitative desktop data collection method with inductive thematic analysis provided a pivotal outline on the roles of the two sectors in equipping South African youth with relevant skills and knowledge for the ever-changing marketplace. The government policies, journal articles and books were perused to provide insight and expertise knowledge. The findings of the enquiry revealed the critical components relating to the role of the TVET and ACET sectors. Recommendations are done to close the skills gap through the provision of the vocational and adult learning opportunities.

Keywords: Education policies, employment, prospects, roles, TVET, ACET

I. INTRODUCTION

South Africa have fifty (50) Technology and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) colleges and three hundred and sixty-four (364) campuses across rural and urban areas. These colleges are meant to provide practical skills, knowledge and attitudes that are essential in the workplace. Literature confirms that learners will ordinarily consider and prefer the TVET colleges as an alternative choice than the traditional academic routes of universities. This was discovered through a growing interest in learners to enrol in the colleges as they provide courses and training programmes leading to employment (Wattanasin, Chatwattana & Piriyaasurawong, 2021). The students who are enrolled are expected to go through a transition from school to work as trainees and competent apprentices. South Africa is currently experiencing a high dropout rate of 60% of first graders leaving school before completing Grade 12 which is already described as a national crisis and 52% of the age-appropriate population remain enrolled by Grade 12 (Van der Merwe, 2020).

Education experts in the sector attest that the social and economic trends necessitate the urgency to reform the TVET Systems with the intention to create renewed development pattern which holds a culture of economically, environmentally and socially sustainable development. They strongly assert that the sector should be able to provide training opportunities and career advancement avenues for majority of learners

from schools and also provide skills that are applicable for the economy. The sector does not receive the respect it deserves as it is regarded at the periphery and its value is not yet fully embraced. This predicament leaves the mandate of Technical Colleges (TVET) to primarily be at the same level of teaching like any other high school can do (Sebola, 2022).

On the other hand, the number of illiterate people in South Africa is high and reflecting on the consequences of apartheid on the Adult Community Education and Training (ACET) vocational skills are critical to be developed to partake in the mainstream economy. Though the limitation of Adult Education and Training, its disregard for formal qualifications of learners, conventional approaches to the programmes negatively influence their progression towards a formal skills development career opportunities (Bowl, 2017). The adult learning practitioners together with those who are involved in community development are of the opinion that adult learning should play a role in assisting communities to engage in the processes of transformation (Baatjies, 2003). It is of paramount importance to still address the challenges of social and economic conditions created by the past through relevant approaches.

The reality on the ground is that the TVET and ACET centres are offering the so called Adult Basic Education and Training (ABET) and Adult Community Education and Training (ACET) through formal and informal learning modes towards a general education. Some of these centres still offer skills courses such as technology, career guidance, study and writing skills as well as agricultural and other livelihoods skills; democracy and human rights, gender and domestic violence, social and economic rights and advocacy (Land, 2021). All these courses are a result of prioritising profit and commodification of education hence the sector is underfunded when compared to other schooling and post-school education sectors (Benavot, 2018). TVET and ACET has been regarded as an important learning opportunity for achieving social equity, inclusion and sustainable development in the country.

Though the South African government made sincere efforts to change the latter through the implementation of relevant policies (Daniels, 2020) to make Adult Education and Training and Community Education and Training a formal education system, its status to formally offer recognised qualifications is still not fulfilled. The policies changed the function of the ACET from only providing opportunities for the out of school youth and marginalised adults to acquire literacy and opportunities to improve their work prospects (Daniels, 2020; RSA DoE, 2000).

II. DISTINCT CHARACTERISTICS OF THE TVET AND ACET SECTORS

The distinctive nature of the three sectors may be confusing as a result of their unintentional, or incidental nature (Singh, 2015). Some experts accept their discursive nature referring to formal, non-formal and informal learning (Johnson & Majewska, 2022).

Table 1: The distinct characteristics of adult education

TVET	ACET
<p>‘It is an integral part of general education. a means of preparing for occupational fields and effective participation in the world of work’.</p> <p>‘It is an aspect of lifelong learning and a preparation for responsible citizenship. an instrument for promoting environmentally sound sustainable development’.</p>	<p>‘It is a broad concept that includes all the learning opportunities that all people want or need after completion of a Literacy programme and primary education’.</p> <p>(Eraut, 2004)</p> <p>‘It is a planned, organised learning acts designed to maintain, improve, or expand knowledge and</p>

<p>It is a method of facilitating poverty alleviation. (UNESCO, 2009)</p>	<p>skills in order for the students to develop new knowledge and skills relevant to the enhancement of practice, education, or theory development to improve their lives and others'. (Baatjies & Baatjies, 2008)</p>
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In support of the listed characteristics of the TVET and ACET sectors, the Global Report on Adult Learning and Education revealed almost similar outcomes that adult education is a powerful tool for eradicating poverty and acquiring skills for sustainable economic development (UIL, 2009). It evident that the institution of adult education was neglected in many countries which has resulted in a condition where many of the youths, particularly South African women, are faced with the problem of poverty and unemployment.

Other studies on adult education and training revealed that ACET programmes are designed to reward learners with certificates to use in the for job hunting after their studies (Umalusi, 2008). These certificates are of low quality and not relevant to the job market (Mayer, Gordhan, Manxeba, Hughes, Foley, Maroc, Lolwana, & Nell, 2011). The interconnectedness of the formal, informal and non-formal education goes beyond normal classroom experiences (Eaton, 2010).

- Formal education or learning is organized, guided by a formal curriculum, leads to a formally recognized credential
- Informal education or learning do not involve a formal curriculum and no credits are earned and someone with more experience
- Non-formal education and learning is organized and may or may not be guided by a formal curriculum, but is highly enriching and builds an individual's skills and capacities

III. WHAT WENT WRONG IN THE TVET AND ACET SECTORS?

When the Further Education and Training (FET) Colleges Act (2006) was passed, 128 technical colleges were formalised into 50 new public FET colleges. The Act made those colleges through the New Institutional Landscape Policy implemented by the Department of Education in 2001, the juristic bodies with governing councils. This signalled a significant privatisation intervention. As part of the merger process, all FET college staff were simultaneously transferred from the employ of their provincial education department to become FET College Council employees.

Akoojee (2008) raised a concern about the varying levels of expertise on college councils that had the potential to reinforce existing inequities between historically privileged colleges, on the one hand, and under-resourced colleges. With workplace training being located under the Department of Labour (DoL's) learnership system, the public FET colleges increasingly focused on initial vocational training for pre-employed learners. The colleges were increasingly focusing on theoretical inputs and less on artisanship and skills training for the workplace.

The more academic NC(V) programmes were put in place to replace the NATED artisan programmes. This was done in a very centralised way, with few economic areas being consulted. The goal of these programmes was to help pupils get accepted to college and find work (DoE, 2006b). But the TVET schools couldn't keep the industry trainers who worked with students on internships, and they also couldn't build their own skills (Needham & Papier, 2018). The fact that the public FET colleges were not ready or equipped for the start of the NC(V) programmes was not taken into account in the choice. As a result, the first group of NC(V) students had a throughput rate of just over 5% in 2009.

The Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) on the other hand with its mitigating strategies for the infrastructure, governance and management challenges at Community Education and Training

colleges which were established in 2015. DHET had established five-year term councils and appointed managers as permanent employees of the Department.

The challenges confronting the ACET sector are outlined as follows (ACET Colleges update: 2020). These include inherent frustration in building a sector that lacks infrastructure identity, difficulties in the timely filling of vacancies due to exorbitant publishing costs, and conflicts between council and management arising from misunderstandings of roles and responsibilities. Additionally, there is a limited staff component at the managerial level, a lack of staff to receive skills transfer related to systems, a limited budget, challenging conditions of service for lecturers, and a lack of diversity.

The Department of Higher Education made attempts to provide support for the ACET sectors to ensure that teaching and learning happens. The first cohort of councils were appointed in 2015 to perform the oversight role on the management of Centres. This implies that more needs to be done to ensure the efficiency of the sector. The adult education budgets hardly grew and remained a minute proportion as compared to the overall amount of money allocated to state provincial and the national education budgets (Aitchison & Land, 2019).

IV. THE POSITION OF POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

Post-School Education and Training (PSET) Information Policy (2019) was adopted by the Department of Higher Education and Training in 2013 which was meant to replace the Higher Education and Training Information Policy. This marked a transformative interchange of the governance and administration of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) and Adult Community Education and Training (ACET) colleges from provincial education departments to the Department to advance meaningful democracy, transparency, efficiency, transformation and effectiveness in the PSET sector (PSET, 2013).

It is important to realise that the main goal of the White Paper for Post-School Education and Training (2013) was ‘to build an efficient fit between the education and training system and the needs of the economy, a reliable and comprehensive system of data collection, storage and analysis is essential’. The policy is aimed to improve the capacity of the post-school education and training system to meet South Africa’s needs. This policy recognises that the current system are fragmented; and an integrated management information system consisting of institutional and labour market data should be generated over time to inform the Minister of the progress made in achieving the goal.

As set out by the policy, some of its objectives related to the TVET and ACET sectors include assisting in building a fair, equitable, non-racial, non-sexist, and democratic South Africa. Additionally, the policy aims to build a single, coordinated post-school education and training system, and to expand access, improve quality, and increase diversity in education and training opportunities.

The main concern that would ascend from the prominent evidence regarding protests by the students on the ability of the government to improve the management and governance, develop the quality of teaching and learning, increase responsiveness to local labour markets, improve student support services, and develop their infrastructure. The key question to consider is whether the policy is achieving its set objectives.

It has been acknowledged that the current mix of programmes and qualifications in the TVET colleges is challenging to administer and poorly qualified assured, which instil fear for students and their families (White Paper for Post-School Education and Training, 2013). These programmes require a thorough and collective review and rationalisation between Department of Higher Education (DHET) and Department of Basic Education (DBE); the colleges, employees and the relevant unions to ensure that there is differentiated college system with various niche areas of specialisation.

The Adult Community and Training colleges were established as alternative career pathway for the youth and adults who did not complete their schooling and have limited opportunities for structured learning, including learners with disabilities; and thus, do not qualify to study at TVET colleges and universities (White Paper for Post-School Education and Training, 2013). The colleges exist as multi-campus institutions called public adult learning centres.

The following basic principles underpin the establishment and declaration of Community Education and Training colleges, providing a clear mandate for the Department of Higher Education regarding the sector. These principles include the expansion of access to education and training for all youth and adults, the promotion of the goals and objectives of a progressive socio-economic agenda, the provision of good quality formal and non-formal education and training programs, and the provision of vocational training to prepare individuals for participation in both the formal and informal economies.

In this article, it is important to place these principles in line with the context of the Continuing Education and Training Act, 2006 and to conclude if the objectives are met.

V. INTERNATIONAL POST-SCHOOL TRENDS

The profiles of the international world of education changes constantly to improve the way students learn, institutions function, and the dynamic and transformational world of work. These developments require students to be well-informed, prepared and willing to adapt to the evolving education landscape. They face challenges to embark on a truly transformative educational career journey that offers them a wealth of experiences and available opportunities.

The most developed countries gain prominence in the competitive global economy. To mention some of these countries offering advanced learning opportunities (Dzhurylo, 2019; Tan, 2022; OECD, 2023, Pont, 2004):

- *Germany: 'known for its commitment to quality education and strong emphasis on research attracting students from around the world'.*
- *Netherlands: 'known for its innovative approach to education and research and is becoming a favourite among international students'.*
- *Ireland: 'becoming a hub for education in the fields of Technology and Business and does welcome environment for international students.'*
- *New Zealand: 'known for providing a top-tier education system and is becoming a desirable choice for those seeking excellent education'*
- *Singapore: 'known for being a hotspot for attracting students pursuing degrees in Business, Technology and Engineering'.*

These international sceneries of education are constantly changing in response to the labour market. Countries like the United States, the Community Colleges play a dual role of as an institution for market skilling and for the transition to higher education (Garrod, 2009). The improvements in the international post-school training and education has since gained status in the labour market as a result of the emphasis on the information technology (IT) and communication skills (Levy & Murnane, 2004).

The South African Adult Education contexts is characterised by the attracting students who are likely to be academically weak with limited theoretical knowledge (Lolwana, 2010). The South African education systems are found to be attracting the products of low socioeconomic status backgrounds and ineffective school systems and this widens the gap of access to formal post-school education. It is consequently advisable that other countries eliminate the exclusionary elements of post-school system to widen access in higher education (UNESCO, 2015).

VI. THE NATIONAL YOUTH CRISIS

The high rates of unemployment among South African youth has resulted in them seeking some type of a qualification to be able to find employment or a better job (Lolwana, 2010). They would opt to study in the TVET and ACET sector. However, the government envisage the expansion of the sectors, the high levels of drop-out in South Africa has worsened the chances for TVET and ACET sectors to support students academically (Field, Musset & Álvarez-Galván, 2014). The provision of career guidance and student support also have reached the apathy levels. The students are not encouraged to complete their studies.

The current position of the ACET programmes indicates that few training centres are available and for those available are far in between thus limiting access and paving the way for learners to access the TVET institutions instead (Akoojee, 2012).

On the other hand, the TVET sector across Africa is still characterized by several challenges, as highlighted by Oviawe (2020). These challenges include low-quality training and a mismatch between training and labor market skill demands. Additionally, the sector suffers from poor facilities such as

workshops, books, classrooms, learning environments, machines, computer rooms, TV/audio visual equipment, and inadequate curriculum content across most campuses. There are also issues with inadequate classrooms, a lack of staff offices, insufficient electricity and water supply, inadequate workshop spaces, and a lack of essential TVET machines and tools. Furthermore, there is a shortage of textbooks, consumable materials, and instructional materials. This is as a result of high amounts of the expenditure on staffing with little funds remaining for infrastructure (DHET, 2016).

VII. THE IMPORTANCE OF TVET AND ACET SECTOR IMPROVEMENT PLANS

When the DHET was established in 2009, its mandate was the development human resources of the workforce in an inclusive way (Field, Musset & Álvarez-Galván, 2014). The Department instituted the post-school system comprising of university and college sector, adult learning centres, the private institutions, the Sector Education and Training Authorities (SETAs), the National Skills Fund (NSF) and the regulatory bodies to be responsible for qualifications and quality assurance. The government's further took a decision to implement the National Development Plan of the White Paper for Post-school Education and Training System 2019–2030 which highlighted a very positive move toward transforming the TVET and ACET sectors (DHET, 2019b). Its objective was that by 2030, a million learners should have been registered in the new Community Education and Training College (CETC) system. This was a necessary step to steadily increase a stream of adult learners into the state system but in vain (Aitchison, 2018).

VIII. WHAT NEEDS TO BE IMPROVED FOR THE SECTORS TO BE FUNCTIONAL?

By drawing from the report of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries by (Pont, 2004) on the changes in the adult learning and education, ways to increase access to different types of adult learning through public provision, improvements could be initiated to improve the vocational and adult learning sectors.

Adult and vocational learning is currently receiving more attention from most of the governments (Pont, 2004). With this happening, the policies for adult learning are well developed and clear, the approaches are not completely developed. It is important to provide coherence and coordination among many different partners who are involved in the development and planning on related activities.

The sector requires more suitable pedagogy to attract adult learners (Pont, 2004). The supply of participants in other programmes is very limited because of the sector not able to meet the demand. The programmes should provide flexible schedules for adult learners to be able attend to their family commitments and to cap unemployment. Investment in learning should target those without learning opportunities, skills and educational qualifications to reach potential demand of the sector.

It is important to evaluate the adult learning programmes to measure their impact and to improve the policy design, rationalise the limited resources and coordinate the different stakeholders (Pont, 2004). It is actual that the public training programmes other target groups at the expense of those who are in need. The process of quality control of the adult learning programmes could allow the government to define standards and conditions to access training. Integrated quality management systems could provide clarity on the criteria for public funding.

It is important provide proper guidance and counselling systems for adult learners to make appropriate learning opportunities and options (Pont, 2004). The overall spending patterns in adult learning seem to be complex and could as it include al adult education, vocational adult education, basic skills education, general non-vocational education, labour market training for the unemployed or those at risk, and enterprise-based training and this put pressure on the government funding.

It is strongly urged that the stakeholder of the adult training and education prioritise the fulfilment of the goal of overcoming current existing barriers to access and participation in adult education programmes (European Union, 2012). Firstly, the structural barriers that hampering or discouraging participation due to the non-flexible education delivery systems or lack of access to adequate funding. There should be a radical change of perceptions through the promotion of available career options. Secondly, situational barriers that arise from individual circumstances because of age or family life. There is a need for awareness development activities and learning opportunities suited to the youth needs. Lastly, psychological barriers relating to life experiences due to negative associations with the schooling environment, lack of confidence, sense of

worthlessness, or social exclusion. There is a need to develop societal interest and introduce activities that overcome traditional fears of education.

IX. THEORETICAL VIEWPOINT AND ITS RELEVANCE TO THESE SECTORS

Koehler and Mishra (2005) describe the three core components of knowledge in the Technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) framework that consists of the content knowledge (CK), pedagogical knowledge (PK), and technological knowledge (TK). This framework relates to TVET training. Prolific studies have employed TPACK to investigate vocational education teachers' competencies and documented empirical evidence for an in-depth understanding of vocational education teachers' competencies. There was a tendency to emphasise the development of technological knowledge over the development of pedagogical and content knowledge, which could be integrated into teaching (Ran and Cai, 2017).

It is beneficial to take cognisance of the principles of adult learning which is a process of adults gaining knowledge and expertise (Knowles, Holton & Swanson 2005). These learners will have many different backgrounds, learning styles, motivation, and needs that must be considered in the learning process. Some bring with experience and are outside responsibilities and approach learning situations with their own strengths and challenges. Andragogy is the adult theory that refers to "the art and science of helping adults learn (Knowles, 1984). Adult learning theories provide insight into how adults learn and can help instructors be more effective in their practice and more responsive to the needs of the learners they serve. Knowles (Knowles et al., 2005) provides assumptions on adult learning that offer a clear understanding of this process. These assumptions include the idea that adults learn what they need to know, and learners must be aware of this essential need. Facilitators of adult learning should incorporate this principle into the design of learning programs. Additionally, adults are responsible for their own learning, and the experiences of learners play a crucial role in the learning process. Adult learners are problem-centered in their orientation to learning and respond to external motivators, although internal motivation tends to be more powerful.

X. METHODS

In pursuing the study, the qualitative research approach of generating existing data was employed. The qualitative research approach with its multimethod focus involves an interpretive, naturalistic style to its subject matter (Denzin and Lincoln, 1994; Creswell & Creswell, 2018). This approach allows the study of natural settings in an attempt to make sense of, or interpret, the phenomenon in terms of the meanings created by others. This article explored the role of TVET and ACET sectors in improving the employment prospects of the youth in South Africa. With qualitative research, the social reality of individuals, groups, and cultures are well understood. Thus, people and groups are studied in their natural setting (Creswell, 2013).

The purposive sampling of secondary data sources was used to gain in-depth view of the phenomena (Shaheen, Gupta, & Kumar, 2016). The main goal of purposive sampling is to identify the cases, individuals, or communities that are best suited to helping you answer the research question (Nikolopoulou, 2023). The information-rich cases that contained issues that are important for the research and to help answer the research objectives were considered. The purposive maximum variation sampling used to capture the widest range of perspectives possible and to identify important common patterns that are true across variations of selected cases (Nikolopoulou, 2023).

A qualitative case study design of the two (TVET and ACET) sectors are explored to gain in-depth understanding of the roles of their existence in real-life and contemporary contexts (Yin, 2015; Stake, 1995). A variety of data obtained from sustained sources provided detailed information (Yin, 2009, 2014) to respond to the issues to be explored. Denzin and Lincoln (2000) highlight several characteristics of qualitative research that guide this study. They describe qualitative research methodology as a dynamic approach that enables the study of the complexities of human behavior, opinions, and experiences through contextual, grounded insights. This methodology involves a process of naturalistic inquiry aimed at gaining an in-depth understanding of social phenomena within their natural settings. It systematically employs a predefined set of procedures to answer questions, collect evidence, and produce findings that are not predetermined, ensuring that the results are applicable beyond the scope of the study.

XI. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The qualitative desktop research review was used to gain more insights and draw conclusions from existing knowledge and expertise (Foley, 2019) on the role of TVET and ACET sectors in improving the employment prospects of youth in South Africa. The existing secondary literature and studies relating to the topic of this article were systematically reviewed and analysed (Fitchburg State University, 2020). The data was sourced from the academic journal articles, education textbooks, authentic internet websites and relevant dissertations/thesis.

Qualitative data analysis provided a systematic process of examining and interpreting non-numerical data to gain meaningful insights and generate new knowledge and to gain a comprehensive understanding of complex social issues from the data sources (Moser & Korstjens, 2018). A clear understanding of the research context and the social, cultural, and historical factors that shape it was reached (Gibbs, 2007). The thematic data analysis method considered by (Braun and Clark, 2006) was iterative in generating meaningful data codes. This method allows for the identification of patterns and themes in qualitative data. The inductive thematic data analysis facilitated the inducement of views, and opinions from the generated data (Aronson, 1994; Boyatzis, 1998). Data codes were created to identify and summarise important concepts related to the main themes of the set data (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The patterns of meaningful themes were interpreted to make sense of the data.

For the purpose of this article, the following phases of the thematic analysis approach will unfold to ensure that the themes of interest are alluded (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Dawadi, 2020; Chamberlain, 2015):

- *Familiarising with the data by conducting repeated careful reading of the texts to be fully immersed in the data and collect initial points of interest*
- *Generating initial codes by selecting phrases or sentences/paragraphs that were of interest from the relevant extracts*
- *Searching for the themes by identifying a list of codes across the data set that represent a pattern of themes to be generated into potential themes*
- *Reviewing themes by refining the initially grouped themes to be presented in a systematic*
- *Defining and naming the themes by refining and defining their essence for to what they are captured for*
- *Writing report by providing a concise, coherent and logical account of the story that the data represented within and across themes, which will serve as evidence that captured the essence of the overall data.*

FIGURE 1: THEMATIC OVERVIEW (THEMES AND SUB-THEMES)

XII. DISCUSSIONS

This article is premised towards the transformative philosophical assumptions that provides an action agenda for reform of the marginalised groups (Mertens, 2010). This philosophical worldview maintains that their specific social issues hold the central place and should need to be addressed to subvert the inequalities based on socio-economic class and power relations. The majority of student who dropout of the TVET and ACET sectors in view of these assumptions could empowered to have a voice and participate in the economic spaces.

The uncovered major issues of the three sectors (TVET and ACET) sectors are a lack of access to resources and class allocation challenges that are exacerbated by over-enrolment. An Auditor General's report linked the poor success rates of adult learners to the poor quality of teaching by underqualified educators who struggled to interpret the curriculum and lacked basic teaching skills and strategies Auditor-General's (2014).

The major goals of adult education is to bring about improvements in the quality of lives of the individuals and enable them to realise their potential for self-realisation (Houle, 1972). It raises the standard of living in the families, communities, societies and nation and promote peace and communal harmony in the multi-cultural global village. Adult education also bring about augmentation of the pace of development and welfare of the individual nations and international community as a whole. A number of studies concur that adult education is a powerful tool for favouring inclusive development through democracy (Seya, 2014).

The adult education is crucial in providing a platform for personal growth and self-improvement among the marginalised groups (Fujiwara & Campbell, 2011). It can allow individuals to fulfil their intellectual curiosity, learn new skills, and pursue their passions. The adult learners are able to learn new language, acquiring digital skills or even exploring aspired interests as continuous learning enriches lives and boosts self-esteem. Some prominent theories has shared the light on the transformative learning, self-directed learning, experiential learning, and andragogy, which suitably characterise adult education, and:

'Adult education is a catalyst for social integration and community engagement. It brings diverse groups of people together, fostering a sense of community and encouraging intercultural understanding. By participating in adult learning programs, individuals develop social connections, contribute to community initiatives, and promote positive social change'.

The following discussion focuses on various themes and sub-themes are generated from a fountain of data collected from the comprehensive literature search.

Figure 1 provides the list of key themes and the sub-themes or a thematic overview the role of the TVET and ACET sectors that will be independently discussed to systematically organise and analyse complex data sets (King, 2004).

Main theme: Roles of TVET, ACET

Sub-theme 1: Roles of policies

The policy development on adult education in South Africa marked the steps towards achieving development and transformation of the sectors. There is still an impression that the transformation will be an ongoing process of creating an enabling environment wherein the adult educator in government and other providers such as non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and providers in the economic sector, can continue to coordinate their efforts and co-operate across sector.

The Further Education and Training Act of 1998 does a lot of different things. It sets rules for further education and training, creates, runs, and pays for state institutions for this purpose, and lets private institutions in this area get registered. The Act also makes sure that higher education and training are of high quality and promotes them. It also makes transitional plans easier and gets rid of old laws while dealing with related issues.

The Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) also wants to make the system for education and training after high school better able to meet the needs of the country. A white paper from 2013 called the White Paper for Post-School Education and Training tells the DHET and its affiliated schools how they can help build a developmental state with a strong democracy and a thriving economy. This policy lays out plans to make the system for education and training after school better able to meet South Africa's needs.

The National Plan for Post-School Education and Training 2019–2030 spells out the main goals, outcomes, strategies, and plans that are needed to make the post-school education and training system unified, coordinated, expanded, responsive, cooperative, quality, efficient, successful, and well-thought-out.

Sub-theme 2: Social and economic transformation

Though the concept of adult education has undergone significant transformation (Eruka and Ieeve, 2011), it is important to acknowledge the real needs of disadvantaged adults in education, which is aggravated by poverty cycles. Prolific literature concede that the social and economic status of the adult education sectors still depicts the high levels of inequalities or have worsened the social inequality for not increasing advantages for accessing better education opportunities. The challenges faced by youth are the provision of learning opportunities, which impacts on the economy, and the levels of social mobility. The situation similarly affects accessibility or flexible learning to a broader cohort of adults. The high levels of school dropout among school and unemployment are rising annually. The evaluation of the adult education programmes also form part of the socio-economic transformation.

Sub-theme 3: Vocational skills and knowledge

Literature confirm that it is important to have the right skill sets to make yourself employable and attractive to employers. By knowing the different vocational skills one can acquire one is able to choose a good career path and prepare oneself for the work environment. The individual becomes competent. These skill and knowledge are essential for changing world of work.

The formal learning follows a syllabus and is intentional in the sense that learning is the goal of all the activities learners engage in. The non-formal learning takes place outside formal learning environments but within some kind of organisational framework. The informal learning takes place outside schools and colleges and arises from the learner's involvement in activities that are not undertaken with a learning purpose in mind. National Certificate Vocational allows students to master a specific set of skills in preparation for the workplace. This means that without finishing Matric, students get the chance to harness their skills and build a successful career. They are offered on NQF levels 2 (Grade 10), 3 (Grade 11) and 4 (Grade 12). NATED courses use both theoretical and practical teachings to give students the best career-based learning. They are offered on NQF levels 1- 6. The National Plan for Post-School Education and Training 2019-2030 is aimed at attracting students. The indicated programmes are hoped to improve the prospects of work and career among the youth; develop competencies and also to provide knowledge and expertise. ABET training teaches basic education skills. This includes basic numbers of skills, as well as the ability to read and write.

Sub-theme 4: Principles of adult education

Literature confirms that limited access to quality adult education programs is not only unique to South Africa but is also an international problem. Adult education can play a fundamental role in tackling many of the growing inequalities by improving wellbeing, self-confidence, social inclusion, as well as employability and economic conditions, adult education can decisively contribute to building communities that would reflect social justice, cohesion, solidarity, and provide equal opportunities for all of its citizens (Kearsley, 2010). Considering the predictable high sense self-direction and motivation of adults, the adult education programmes could facilitate active learning if they are geared towards achievement of goals.

In this article, it was evident that the TVET and ACET sectors could improve the livelihood of the youth of South Africa. Although it is unavoidable to express the financial challenges within the sectors, more needs to be done to improve these sectors.

XIII. CONCLUSION

It could be concluded that 'South Africa's neo-liberal economic approach has enabled neither of these education and training systems to effectively produce TVET graduates who help to overcome the critical skills shortages and contribute to national economic growth'. Kraak (2008) pointed out that the emphasis on training unemployed learners arose from a Growth and Development Summit in 2003 that emphasised the need for training for unemployed youth, which could be a catalyst for social transformation.

Renowned adult education specialists recommended that the government should use graduates from the TVETs and ACET in the appropriate disciplines and ideally fund them with bursaries committing that they will spend an equivalent time in the government department upon graduation. This initiative can be a collaborative effort with the DHET in assisting TVETs and ACET in raising their profiles. The implementation of the national strategy where major national companies get involved could develop and assist in implementing to collaborate with specific TVETs and ACET across the country. They also advocate the necessity to maximise the use of ICT to improve the quality and quantity of the adult education to improve the quality of learning.

In a study conducted by Motschilnig (2014), adult learning was met with some unexplainable shortcomings ranging from limitations in knowledge base, focus in attainment for formal education; human capital and economic outcome; focus on vocational training; transferability of skills and methodological challenges of evaluating the programmes.

Kraak (2013) advocates that an 'employer-led demand intervention for skills through sectoral skills councils as a 'radical departure from the centralised and statist approaches of the UK and South Africa' could be an inspiration. This intervention should promote localised entities with a remit to influence employers to promote competitive strategies. Kraak notes the lack of employer support for vocational training and the low levels of employment of graduates with vocational qualifications internationally and locally.

For the sectors to make an impact, adults have to see the benefit, value and purpose of learning and for them to be effective learners, they must be able to identify their own needs and take responsibility for their own learning. This means that adults are responsible for managing their time and setting priorities

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